

INFECTION CONFIRMATION

There is no perfect tool to diagnose canine *B. canis* infection. For correct diagnostics the schematic workflow was developed combining repeated sampling and indirect serological testing four to six weeks apart, coupled with direct isolation or DNA detection, either from blood or various available tissues and bodily fluids. These options were put together by a panel of scientists from partners countries. These testing algorithms will vary locally depending on epidemiological, diagnostic and regulatory factors. These suggestions are not intended to be an imperative for the management of brucellosis cases in dogs but rather a set of recommendations in different epidemiological contexts.

B. canis strain characterisation

To characterise isolated *B. canis* strains schematic workflow is proposed including all validated genomic and phenotyping methods. For each characterisation method, dedicated SOP has been validated and is available.

